

A Perceived Suggestion to Improve the Educational Outcomes of Colleges of Education at Jordanian Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 07, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Education Outcomes, Colleges Of Education, Jordanian Universities</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4499158</p>	<p><i>The purpose of the present study was to identify the reality of, and to make a perceived suggestion that helps improve, the educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities. This was done through uncovering the ways and means that contribute to improving the education outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities. An attempt was made to answer the following main question and the secondary questions that were emanated from it: What is the perceived suggestion to improve the educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities? To this end, the descriptive, analytical method was used. Furthermore, the strengths, weaknesses, and current and future challenges of improving education outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities were determined. Many results were yielded and many recommendations were made to improve the outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities. Results and recommendations were presented clearly and simplistically, and can be applied practically in colleges of education.</i></p>

Introduction

Education systems of all countries, in order to ensure quality, face challenges. This is especially true as the success of educational institutions is measured by the efficiency of alumni and their ability to serve the society and meet the demands of labor market (Aljawarneh & Atan, 2018). The reports made by international organizations emphasize the necessity to reconsider the philosophy of university education. According to these reports, an attempt should be made to establish better standards in order to produce quality educational outcomes, which are expected to encourage individuals to serve their society and support their national culture, (Al-Khamisi, 2007).

It is now necessary to continuously improve and enhance teacher preparation system in colleges of education (Aljawarneh et al., 2020). This can be done through the educational preparation program, whereby the teacher, in the college of education and before getting involved in teaching, improves culturally, scientifically and educationally (Ghanimah, 1996).

As a result of the recent changes of the current era, such new concepts as 'globalization' and 'communication and information technology revolution' came into existence on a professional level (Alsafadi et al., 2020). These concepts had an effect on teacher preparation theories, in such a way that it was inevitable to reconsider the teacher preparation system so it becomes more suitable to the modern demands (Al-Omari et al., 2020). Therefore, universities in general and colleges of education in particular became obligated to rethink their methods and data to achieve sustainable development (Al-Bohairi, 2005). Also, to close the gap between theory and practice, and to make the output suitable for the labor market, an effort should be made to enhance educational outcomes of the colleges of education (Alshare et al., 2020). In this regard, universities, by preparing and improving human capabilities, should play a role in supporting inclusive development plans for all sectors.

The Research Problem and Questions

To improve the quality of university education, higher education institutions in Arabian countries try to imitate and emulate the expertise and experience of western education institutions (Abu Fareh, 2004). In fact, the alumnus possesses some characteristics that are in accordance with the international standards for academic programs. Such characteristics include the knowledge and ability that an alumnus gains after taking a certain course or academic program. Higher education institutions endeavor to produce outcomes accurately, so the latter can meet the needs of society and labor market and improve both of them in light of the future changes in skills and knowledge (The Guide for Writing Learning Outcomes, 2017).

What has been presented so far shows that outcomes are the purpose of existence of any system. Furthermore, the outcomes indicate the soundness and advancement of the system. Hence, all education institutions, regardless of their type, always endeavor to enhance their outcomes.

One of the main problems facing the Jordanian higher education is the incompatibility of the abilities of the alumni and the demands of labor market. The quality of educational outcomes of Jordanian universities is generally low—does not meet the standards of international universities. Therefore, it is necessary to improve

the quality of educational outcomes in general and outcomes of the colleges of education in particular, because this quality directly affects all sectors of labor market. Based on what has been presented thus far, the research problem can be known by answering the following main question:

What is the perceived suggestion to improve the educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities?

Of this main question, the following secondary questions are raised:

- 1-What is the reality of the quality of educational outcomes in colleges of education at Jordanian universities?
- 2-What is the mechanism for improving colleges of education at Jordanian universities to enhance their outcomes?
- 3-What are the indicators of improvement of outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities?
- 4-What is the perceived suggestion to enhance the outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities?

The Research Objective:

This research seeks to make a suggestion on how to enhance educational outcomes in colleges of education at Jordanian universities. This is done by:

- 1-Casting light on the reality of the quality of educational outcomes in the colleges of education at Jordanian universities.
- 2-Explaining the mechanism that colleges of education at Jordanian universities adopt to develop programs aiming to enhance their outcomes.
- 3-Illustrating the indicators of enhancement of outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities.
- 4-Making a suggestion to enhance the outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities.

The Research Significance:

The significance of this research lies in the significance of its topic. In other words, it is necessary to enhance the educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities. Outcomes must possess a high degree of skill and higher education institutions must be dedicated in this regard. By doing so, it is aimed that persons master the teaching skills, and that they be obligated to gain experience, beside learning theories (Arab League Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organization, 2000).

It is hoped that the following parties benefit from the results and recommendations of this study and enhance the educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities:

- 1-Decision-makers of Jordanian universities and Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research
- 2-Scholars; in order to raise more questions and conduct more research and studies related to enhancing the quality of educational outcomes in colleges of education at Jordanian universities

Given that colleges of education aim at preparing teachers who themselves prepare generations, the task of these colleges significantly affects society and its development.

Boundaries of the Research:

Subject boundaries: The educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities.

Spatial boundaries: This study was limited only to colleges of education at Jordanian universities.

The Study Terms:

Educational outcomes:

College of education: Operationally defined by the researcher as, 'Colleges located at Jordanian universities that attempt to perform the education policy and provide manpower that possesses a high level of scientific efficacy which is required to work in the fields of education, psychology and the related qualitative specializations(Alomari et al., 2020). These colleges endeavor to promote and improve research in the fields of education and psychology, but also try to satisfy the needs of society for educational and psychological services.'

Quality in Education: It is a process that aims to increase the learner`s awareness of, and dedication to, quality in terms of knowledge, practice, theories and application. Furthermore, this process provides the teacher with information and skills, and develops his tendencies, intentions and values that help him perform the principles and concepts of quality in his everyday life (Al-Bandari and To`aimah, 2002).

The Population and Sample of the Research:

The present study aimed at educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities. The population of the research included the systems, programs and working mechanism of colleges of education at Jordanian universities. The sample included the outcomes of these colleges.

The Research Methodology

To achieve the objectives of the research and to answer its questions, the descriptive, analytical method was used. This is one of the most suitable methods for this study. Based on this method, facts and information are collected, compared, analyzed, explained and, subsequently, generalized in a satisfactory way. Furthermore, this method describes the educational outcomes of colleges of education actually. After this description, the results are analyzed, and conclusions and recommendations necessary for enhancing the educational outcomes of colleges of education are made. This method, which describes the outcomes accurately, was employed to identify the ways that enhance the educational outcomes of the colleges of education at Jordanian universities.

To put it more explicitly, the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the present study have been illustrated and analyzed to reach realistic results and recommendations.

Previous Studies:

A study by Al-Sharif (2017) under the title: **Quality of learning and teaching in the educational colleges at the emerging Saudi universities in light of the standards of the National Commission for Evaluation and Academic Accreditation.**

This study aimed to identify the degree of applying quality learning and teaching. Also, suggestions were made to enhance the quality of learning and teaching in education colleges at emerging Saudi universities. The population of the study consisted of all faculty members of education colleges at emerging Saudi universities. This study reached a number of results, the paramount of which is that the degree of applying the quality learning and teaching based on the standards of the National Saudi Commission for Evaluation and Academic Accreditation in education colleges at Saudi universities is moderate.

A study conducted by Maysam and Saleh (2014) entitled: **The degree of applying the standards of the Commission for Education Programs Accreditation in Higher Education in colleges of education at public Jordanian universities.**

This study aimed to identify the degree of applying the standards of the Commission for Education Programs Accreditation in Higher Education in colleges of education at Jordanian universities. The most important result of this study was that the standards established by Commission for Education Programs Accreditation in Higher Education are to a moderate degree applied in colleges of education at Jordanian universities. Also, in this study it was recommended that construction and facilities, necessary services, and a number of faculty members with different ranks that suit the education programs of colleges of education be provided. Furthermore, it was recommended that a consultation program be provided for students to receive advice. In addition, students should gain relevant information to adapt to educational programs. Universities, according to these recommendations, should be obligated to accreditation standards when developing educational programs.

A study carried out by Al-Najjar (2007) under the title: **Academic accreditation of teacher preparation institutes as a means of quality assurance in general education institutions.**

The purpose of this research was to cast light on the importance of academic accreditation of teacher preparation institutions. An attempt was also made to examine the contribution of these institutions to achieving quality in general education through their alumni—teachers. The most important results of this study were that, for an educational institution to be qualified for being academically accredited, it should meet some basic preconditions. These preconditions include possessing an institutional message which is commensurate with the level of an educational institution. Furthermore, educational quality of the institute should be consistent with the institutional message, as well as the institute should possess sources and resources that are necessary for achieving the educational objectives and for acting on the institute's message. It is also necessary to provide a system for attesting students' practices that are related to the educational objectives.

A study by Kan'an (2003) entitled: **Prospects of improving colleges of education according to the indicators and applications of quality in higher education.**

In this study an attempt was made (1) to investigate the concept 'quality' and its applications in education, (2) to determine the most important criteria and indicators of quality in higher education, (3) to scrutinize the obstacles of applying quality in university education, (4) and to scrutinize the most important procedures that must be followed to assure and maintain total quality for colleges of education. A number of recommendations were made in this study, of which is that the internal regulations of university colleges should be reconsidered and improved according to quality indicators. Furthermore, an effective system should be designated to assess and evaluate the university performance. This includes the assessment and evaluation of the students, faculty members, curricula, the relationship between the university and society, and the way in which resources are used and invested. An Arabic academic accreditation commission should be set up. This commission, which works under the control of Association of Arab Universities, confers quality certification on colleges according to international total quality standards. Finally, the researcher of this study recommended that the Association of Deans of Arab Colleges of Education and its institutes adopt the total quality system and make a list of all colleges of education in the Arab nation. This list also includes the colleges' regulations, plans, experiences, programs and curricula, so one can turn to them when forming a judgement according to the standards and indicators of total quality about the reality of the colleges.

A study by Al-Fawal (2003) entitled: **Systems of quality and standards accreditation in university colleges and colleges of education.**

The purpose of this study was to shed light on the most important standards of accredited quality in university colleges and colleges of education. A number of quality standards were found to be applied in colleges of education. These standards, which were derived from those established by QAAHE, were divided into different categories. For instance, one category includes the features and standards of evaluation of educational studies; another category includes the structure of evaluation in educational studies; another one concerns the nature of educational studies; still another determines the principles of educational studies.

A study by Al-Bandari and To`aimah (2002) under the title: **Improving colleges of education according to accreditation standards and quality indicators**, Ministry of Higher Education, the Sultanate of Oman.

In this study an attempt was made to cast light on a number of issues related to improving colleges of education, so as to achieve the desired total quality. Furthermore, the justifications and determinants of improvement, as well as quality indicators and a number of standards were discussed. Finally, a number of recommendations were made, of which is that the relationship between colleges of education and primary and secondary schools should be strengthened. In addition, it was recommended that commissions for academic accreditation be established in any Arab country. This should be done to ensure that public universities fulfill the eligibility criteria for establishing colleges of education. Once ensured, a governmental decision will be made to inaugurate these colleges.

It was also recommended that teacher preparation colleges be evaluated every five or ten years, in order to ensure that standards are being met consistently. In addition, more research on total quality system should be done, as well as similar systems and successful experiences should be reviewed to derive their application indicators and to adapt these indicators to the current nature and the social and cultural contexts of colleges of education.

A study conducted by Al-Sa`igh (2003) entitled: **Teacher selection and preparation in Saudi Arabia(A future vision)**.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the teacher preparation system in Saudi Arabia in terms of student and teacher selection, the criteria for finding acceptance in preparation institutes, teacher preparation and training programs, and the conditions of hiring teachers and their professional development. This study illustrated international experiences related to teacher preparation, too. Finally, a future vision was proposed, whereby the teacher should be selected and prepared after going through a procedure. To make it more explicit, the best applicants who can best work as a teacher should be selected. They should be the most moral and intelligent applicants and should possess the highest knowledge of, and skill in, teaching.

According to this vision, preparation programs should be improved to suit the cognitive, social, economic and cultural developments and should be in compliance with education policy constants. Furthermore, in order to enrich, and raise the effectiveness of, preparation programs, state-of-the-art technology should be employed. The abilities and performance of faculty members should be improved, too.

A study carried out by Al-Zahrani (1997) under the title: **The strategic directions for planning the developments of teachers` preparation institutions in Saudi Arabia**.

This study aimed to determine the most strategic directions that can be adopted for planning the development of teacher preparation institutes in Saudi Arabia. These directions concern the following areas: acceptance policy and criteria, objectives of teacher preparation institutes, practical or field education, regulation, planning, and continuous development of teachers. The population of the study comprised Saudi faculty members who work in colleges of education at Saudi universities. This study reached a number of results, the paramount of which is that teacher preparation institutes of the country attach little importance to most strategic directions. In other words, these institutes do not take step according to a clear vision of the development directions. They also demonstrated incompetence in their attempts to improve the teacher preparation program.

The vast majority of the study sample agreed that these directions are appropriate to be adopted for planning the development of teacher preparation institutes in the future. They also emphasized the necessity to make a fundamental change to the policies, criteria and procedure for accepting and selecting students who have enrolled in preparation institutes. For those selected, certain objectives will be set to help them acquire the behavioral and practical skills required for their success and performance improvement. This will also prepare them for field training and help them to improve continuously while serving as teachers.

A study done by Celandia (2004) under the title: **A Study of Iowa Second-Year Teachers` Perception of the Iowa Teaching Standards and Implementation of the Iowa Teacher`s Quality Program**.

This study aimed to investigate the perceptions of Iowa second-year teachers of eight teaching standards. These standards are part of the teacher quality program. The study population comprised second-year students of college of education, the University of Iowa. A number of results were yielded, the most important of which is that programs aiming at qualifying and improving the teacher`s efficacy have strengthened the relationship between trainers, officials and educational supervisors. This has brought a greater opportunity for them to achieve a joint objective. Furthermore, five factors were found to play the most important role in the internship process (practical education) which include clear policies, appropriate resources, enthusiasm and motivation, and convenient economic, political and social circumstances.

Abedin (1992) conducted a study on quality in education. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the scientific efforts made to define quality. Furthermore, this study aimed to present convenient definitions of educational quality, to evaluate the efforts made to measure quality, and to introduce the ways of measuring quality. Results showed that total quality in education comprises some features and characteristics that inclusively and accurately represent the essence and states of education. These features and characteristics

include input, processes, output, feedback, as well as the continuous interactions leading to the achievement of goals which are desirable and appropriate for society.

Abu Hilal et. al. (1998) carried out a study untitled: **The degree of correspondence between higher education and local labor market (An analytical study)**.

This study comprised an introduction and elaborated on the directions of quantitative and qualitative development in higher education. Moreover, the conditions and job status of the alumni, the features of local labor market, and the indicators of the impact of higher education on individuals' personality were discussed. This study also shed light on the causes of weakness of higher education institutes, and proposed a future vision of higher education and labor market. A number of recommendations were also made, including: restructuring and activating the Higher Education Committee, honing the skills of alumni to suit the labor market, and developing the proposed academic programs.

A study was done by Shehadeh (2003) under the title: **Towards A United Arab University Strategy**.

In this study an attempt was made to outline an integrated strategy for Arab universities to confront the challenges facing them in the current century. Furthermore, this strategy aimed to help these universities graduate students having critical thinking, life-long learning and other skills required in the labor market. The alumni are also aimed to be able to live and compete in the globalization era and technological revolution, to feel proud of their Arabic-Islamic heritage and civilization, and to coexist with other civilizations of the world.

This strategy concerns a true transformation, not a false one, and is about both teaching and learning. Furthermore, the student plays a pivotal role in the teaching process and all resources and various activities of the university serve to improve his scientific achievement. This study also elaborated on the corrections that must be made at universities to apply this strategy to them. Such corrections are to be made in the message, academic plans, general education programs, teaching methods, or ways of evaluation at the university.

Commenting on the Previous Studies:

After presenting many previous studies on the issue of developing and enhancing the teaching process and its outcomes, it became obvious that educational quality in general and in colleges of education in particular is moderate. There is a major weakness in applying the standards of Accreditation Commission in colleges of education, too. Many studies recommended providing facilities, constructions and services needed for producing proper outcomes that suit the requirements of the development of society and the needs of labor market. Moreover, it became evident that, at both Arab and global levels, the issue of university educational quality and the issue of total quality management (TQM) have literally gained importance. Furthermore, in order to achieve satisfactory results, the input of colleges of education and the development of the processes of, and mechanism for, outcomes preparation are important. To develop education and to enhance its outcomes in colleges of education, a collaboration between universities, colleges of education, the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Higher Education and other institutions of society is required. As a result of this collaboration, it is aimed that colleges of education at Jordanian universities have a better future.

The Theoretical Framework of the Study:

In any country, the student is regarded as one of the most important educational outcomes of colleges of education in higher education institutes. Any educational program in the colleges of education is accredited by the Education Programs Accreditation Commission. This is done through using TQM standards of the educational system, in order to ensure convenient and qualified educational outcomes and to enhance the administrative and educational performance.

In developed countries, higher education institutes have taken a big step forward in regard to TQM applications. Therefore, higher education institutes in Arab countries are trying to conform and imitate those institutes and replicate their expertise and experience in higher education quality applications (Abu Fareh, 2004). Hence, colleges of education should assume responsibility for preparing the student—the teacher—academically, professionally, culturally and personally. Having said that, most of these proposals are not put into practice in colleges of education. There is also a weakness in the coordination and collaboration between teachers of the theoretical, specialized courses and those of practical courses, thereby the educational outcomes have weakened.

It is as though the program of college of education is composed of separate courses and the student (the future teacher) is often unaware of the justifications and reasons for learning certain issues and performing certain activities. Moreover, most programs of colleges of education are unable to provide the student with the self-learning skill, making him unable to catch up with the changes in the content of curriculum that may result from the scientific and technological development of the modern era. Furthermore, these programs center on the theoretical studies and the practical, applied aspect does not gain enough attention. Education programs do not guide and inspire the student to become involved in the teaching career, nor do they make the student feel he belongs to these areas. These programs were unable to address the problems that face the teacher while teaching, thereby negatively affecting the effectiveness of his performance in different roles (Al-Rashid, 1996).

Answering the First Question:

- What is the reality of the quality of educational outcomes in colleges of education at Jordanian universities?

- Given its major role in continuous enhancement, the issue of quality in educational institutes has grabbed the attention of those concerned. Quality in education is defined by Tenner and Detoro (2000) as, "A basic business strategy that contributes to the provision of products and services. The purpose of this strategy is to satisfy the national and foreign customer and to live up to the customer's expectations." Oshaibah (2000) believes that quality in education consists of a number of standards and features that should be met in all elements of the teaching process, including the input, the processes or the output. Quality in education satisfies the needs and demands of society, but also satisfies the learners' interests and needs. The standards of quality can be met by an active use of all material and human resources.

In their definition of quality in education, Jomiten and Dakar focused on the features of learning. They argued that quality is about desirable learning features. In the teaching process, efficient and knowledgeable teachers are to be involved. They should have knowledge of teaching principles and of integrated and appropriate educational curricula. A just and fair governance system should be present, too (EFA, 2005: 29). Any system, regardless of its size, is undoubtedly composed of three basic elements—input, processes and output—that, in their absence, the system would not operate. This is true of education, too. Therefore, the quality of outcomes of the educational process is a strategy that, by means of information, skills and abilities, aims to achieve continuous enhancement. The quality of outcomes contributes to raising the value of society's institutions (Al-Jawarneh, 2016). Hence, quality comes from the integrated interaction of the output of the educational process, namely the accumulation of specializations, skills and abilities, and the mechanisms and operations of different organizations and sectors that operate based on their own direction and philosophy (Haksen et. al., 2000: 76).

Al-khamisi (2007) believes that quality in education is a process where the educational system fulfills the agreed standards of efficiency and effectiveness of different elements of the educational system (input, processes, output, environment). This will ensure the highest value, efficiency and effectiveness for all objectives of the system and for the expectations of those asking for the educational service (students and society).

Maysam and Saleh (2016) investigated the quality of education programs in higher education in colleges of education at public Jordanian universities. Broadly speaking, they found that all education programs, regardless of their level, are of moderate quality. They also found that academic programs need to be improved urgently and faculty members' level of sustainable professional development should rise (Aljawarneh et al., 2020). The English language should be present in some areas of education, too.

Higher education at Jordanian universities plays a major in preparing human capabilities to think scientifically, to solve problems logically, and to actively assume responsibility, which in turn, develop and improve society. For this reason, official authorities and different groups of society attach much importance to education at Jordanian universities (Farhan, 2000). Majid et. al. (2008) believe that colleges of education at Jordanian universities must review and evaluate their tasks, programs, objectives and policies continuously. Jordanian universities should do so to maintain their basic tasks which are teaching, preparing outstanding faculty members, conducting scientific research, serving the society, providing lifelong education programs, satisfying the cognitive needs of society, and giving scientific, pedagogical and educational advice to all educational and pedagogical sectors of society (Al-Da'abseh, et al., 2018). However, there are many challenges that face the development and improvement of education and reduce its efficiency, effectiveness and quality. The reason behind this is the quantitative increase recently observed in the education sector (Banyhamdan et al., 2020). Furthermore, foreign teaching patterns have been adopted and there is imbalance between educational outcomes and the needs mentioned in national development plans. When selecting high-level administrative officials in colleges of education, efficiency and ability standards are not used either. Note that the education sector in general and colleges of education in particular serve to improve Jordan's economy, and to attract large numbers of students from inside and outside of the country. As a result, official and unofficial authorities attach much weight to education, because it is a major indicator of real development and growth.

Education satisfies the needs and demands of society, too. Therefore, the Jordanian society wants the alumni to possess a high level of efficacy and to acquire skills required in the labor market. It is aimed that Jordan be able to compete regionally and globally. In this regard, the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research took a role, too. To reach the desired quality, it turned to education quality assurance and established some standards for academic accreditation. It is because higher education in Jordan is facing problems such as low efficacy of alumni, imbalance between academic programs and the labor market, shortage of scientific research, and weakness of university administrations (Sabri, 2004). Dagher, Al-Tarawneh and Al-Qudah (2016) carried out a study to identify the degree to which Jordanian higher education outcomes suit the need of labor market. Results indicated that the Jordanian higher education outcomes benefit the need of labor market to a moderate extent. Furthermore, in a study by Al-Tarawneh, Al-Qudah and Dagher (2017), the quality of educational outcomes of Jordanian universities was found to be medium.

To increase the quality of education at Jordanian universities, it is necessary that all those working at these universities make a collective effort. Students, alumni, labor market and society should play an active role, too. Furthermore, given their active role in bringing success to the educational process and in achieving quality in academic programs of universities, the administrative and academic staff play the most important role. In conclusion, all those involved in educational institutes should make a collective effort to achieve high quality in educational programs.

We can identify the quality of the educational process and its outcomes if we understand (1) the relationship between quality and productivity, (2) the relationship between total quality system, and (3) the relationship between quality system and the totality of all areas (ISESCO, 2006). In other words, to enhance the educational quality, it is necessary to make an inspection and comparison to the desired features, and to attach value to the totality perspective. According to this perspective, quality is a philosophy that, in the long-term, plays an important role for the system and all its components to create an organizational culture (Evan, 1997).

The student is one of the most important outcomes of the educational process. Thus, in order for the educational institute to assure quality of this element, it must activate the relationship between the student and society's institutions, before the former gets involved in the labor market. The educational institute should coordinate the government enterprises and labor markets, too, in order to provide job opportunities for graduates. Furthermore, the university should make every effort to improve the level of students, because they are the ultimate product of university and one can through them make a judgement about the general quality of the educational process (Al-Haj et. al., 2008).

Answering the Second Question:

- What is the mechanism for improving colleges of education at Jordanian universities to enhance their outcomes?

To improve the academic programs of colleges of education, all elements of the educational process—material, human and financial ones—should be used ideally, in which case the educational education program can particularly improve. Moreover, for the administrative and academic activities and practices performed by officials, a planned, disciplined and accurate vision should be developed. Such a vision should include all components of education—input, processes and output—so as to satisfy the needs and demands of customers and the labor market (Al-Assaf, 2011).

Education program can be defined as a group of disciplined and distinct courses, whereby one can hold a scientific, academic and specialized degree in this program (Al-Haj, 2008). In other words, education programs are the accumulation of expertise, skills and values that students gain through self-learning and studying the courses that make up the program. Al-Amad (2013) carried out a study to identify the academic accreditation standards and the reality of applying these standards to Jordanian universities. Results indicated that it is possible to apply the general and specific academic accreditation system to Jordanian universities, as experts view. Moreover, Al-Mallah (2005), in consideration of total quality management standards, did a study to identify the reality of education system at Palestinian universities. Findings suggested that, at Palestinian universities, standards of total quality management are met to a moderate extent. Therefore, the researcher of this study recommended enabling the staff to participate in decision-making. It was also recommended to provide periodical training programs in which students participate. All things considered, it is obvious that there is a problem and weakness in academic programs, weakening the educational outcomes directly.

To enhance the outcomes of colleges of education in the way discussed, there are a number of standards that should be concerned (Abu Digha and Arafa, 2007):

- First standard: developing academic programs; students qualified to work as teachers or as other educators should possess skills, as well as cognitive and professional knowledge, and should follow the trends necessary for learning.
- Second standard: the evaluation system; for a college to be accredited, it must implement an evaluation system which delineates what a student is to know, what practice he can perform, and whether he can make a positive contribution to learning.
- Third standard: the practical expertise that the student employs in practice
- Fourth standard: the professional development of faculty members
- Fifth standard: administration and sources; the college has administration, budget, staff, equipment, sources and technologies of information that serve to prepare teacher students to achieve professional quality.

From what has been presented so far we can conclude that, for colleges of education to produce high quality outcomes, they should develop their academic programs and diversify their specializations so as to meet the needs of labor market (Alzoubi et al., 2020). Furthermore, they should train students through practical education; develop faculty members in a suitable way; continuously develop the academic plan of education programs; encourage diversity in evaluation and teaching means; improve the infrastructure in such a way that it meets the requirements of quality teaching; conform to the global and local academic accreditation; produce educational outcomes that, in terms of skill and knowledge, meet the needs of society; and stimulate sustainable development.

Answering the Third Question:

- What are the indicators of improvement of outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities?

Graduates are among the most important outcomes that educational institutes try to improve their quality. These outcomes center on basic knowledge and information that, in turn, form the infrastructure of quality in graduates. Furthermore, knowledge and information are based on two pillars which are capability and capacity of facts related to the operation and profession of fundamental organizations and institutions.

The qualitative level of students rests upon their abilities to have continuity, to comprehend professional bases and principles, and to know the ways of applying their knowledge in practice. In addition, students should possess an open perspective and take different roles. They should also be missionary leaders with a strategic perspective and holistic concentration on the administrative operations and practices of business organizations (Al-Ta'ee, 2005)

There are many indicators of quality of educational outcomes, among which are the number, diversity and inclusivity of outcomes of the educational system. These indicators are compared to the demands of the rapidly-changing nature of the external environment. The nature and diversity of educational institutes' objectives, the effectiveness and efficacy of these institutes, and the circumstances and demands of the surrounding environment lead educational institutes to produce certain outcomes, but not others (Al-Haj, 2008). There are also other indicators and standards of quality of the educational process outcomes that have been introduced by Al-Ta'ee (2005).

Basic knowledge and information form the infrastructure of the quality of graduates. These two elements are based on two pillars that are capability and capacity of facts related to the operation and profession of fundamental organizations and institutions, as well as the professional knowledge of the operations of those organizations. The qualitative level of graduates concerns their abilities to follow and perceive, and their knowledge of practically applying, the professional bases and principles. Yet, the graduate broadens his general perspective, plays different roles, and opens his mind to become a leader with a strategic perspective, and with an inclusive concentration on the administrative operations and practices of business organizations.

It is necessary to strengthen the relationship between society's institutions and the student, before the latter gets engaged in the labor market. It is also necessary to coordinate with the government's institutions and labor markets, in order to provide job opportunities for the graduates. Furthermore, every effort should be made to improve the level of graduates, given that they are the final product and one can through them make a judgement about the educational process quality in general.

It is of paramount importance to concern the input and stages of the educational process, too. Any system, regardless of the nature of its activity, must have input equipped with some important elements that are basically required. These elements should be in agreement with the attitudes, messages, objectives, and the nature of specializations of the system. Furthermore, different circumstances of the environment, as well as the nature and different outcomes of the system should be taken into consideration (Al-Hamali, 2008).

What has been discussed so far shows that the system of the educational process entails further study and accuracy. In fact, it is necessary to accurately study the nature of the components of this system and the relationship between these components and the quality of the educational process in general, and the quality of outcomes in particular, given that outcomes are the ultimate goal that the educational system tries to reach.

Furthermore, we can conclude that there is no educational system that suits all educational institutes. Rather, different institutes have different educational systems. Factors such as the tendency, specializations, facilities, objectives, and the environment of the institute account for this variation. This variation, however, is strongly supportive as it contributes to achieving and assuring the system's outcomes quality.

Answering the Fourth Question:

- What is the perceived suggestion to enhance the outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities?

Higher education institutes keep on transferring the cultural heritage to generations, but also serve the society, search for facts, deal with the continuous changes, contribute to finding solutions for society's problems, and provide the labor market with cadres qualified to satisfy the needs of society and stimulate sustainable development (Al-Dawod, 2007).

To enhance the outcomes of colleges of education—students, basic principles have been established. Achieving this objective entails having knowledge of educational sciences, and having skills and abilities to guide and support students. Furthermore, it is necessary to have familiarity with the social and cultural aspect of teaching, and to regulate the operation of colleges of education in collaboration and partnership with schools and local environment. One should also attach weight to 'the practical education and field expertise' standard, 'variation' standard, 'college administration' standard, and 'faculty members' qualifications, performance and development' standard (Al-Moosawi, 2003).

It is important to focus on educational quality, too. Educational quality, as defined by Sarbu and Ilie (2009), means 'enhancement, committed administration, suitability of goal, anticipated and excellent, and customer satisfaction.' Nicholson, however, defined educational quality as 'the quality of distinguished

performance.’ Moreover, Haksen et. al. (2000) regarded the quality of education outcomes as ‘A strategy whereby information, skills and abilities are employed to enhance continuously. This enhancement helps to put more value on education institutes.’ Therefore, quality is the result of the integrated interaction between the accumulation of specialization, expertise and knowledge of the outcomes of the educational process, and the operations and mechanisms of different organizations and sectors that are based on their own direction and philosophy.

Excellence in teaching: It is the result of preparing professors who form the majority part of the learning process. Professors have a direct impact on university graduates, who had enrolled in educational institutes after their secondary education. Professors also have impact on students who have not entered the university yet (Abu Zina, 2011).

One of the most important reasons for applying total quality to higher education system, as mentioned by ALECSO (2000), is to produce distinguished educational outcomes. This is done by relating quality to productivity, namely through the total quality system that includes all areas and through the universality of quality system, given that it is one of the characteristics of the modern era. Distinguished educational outcomes can also be produced through relating total quality system to total evaluation of teaching in educational institutes.

Quality and excellence are a philosophy that, in the long-term, plays an important role for the organization and all its components to create an organizational culture (Evan, 1997). Increasing the quality of education, as statistics of many countries suggest, can lead to significant economic growth. In other words, as the quality of education increases, economic growth of society promotes, and the income of the individual and society increases, too (Hanusk, E. A., 2005).

Based on what has been presented so far, to enhance the educational outcomes of colleges of education at Jordanian universities, I make the following perceived suggestion:

First: Installing a general evaluation unit that covers the administrative, academic and programmatic systems. It also covers everything related to the input, processes and output of colleges of education. Therefore, all education departments should adhere to this unit for the following reasons:

- International commissions for academic accreditation have required educational institutes to set up an active evaluation system. This is done to accredit the institute and to require colleges of education to conform to high quality standards in terms of preparing graduates. One benefit of this is to save time in academic or institutional accreditation.
- It can help to set objectives and to prepare educational outcomes in the departments of colleges of education. As a result, the problems facing these departments in preparing education outcomes that suit academic accreditation standards will be addressed.
- It helps to evaluate educational outcomes and the performance of the departments of the college, in order to improve their performance based on international standards.
- Reviewing the vision and message of science departments, as well as setting convenient objectives and preparing appropriate educational outcomes would become possible.
- Updating and developing programs of colleges of education in such a way that suit the needs of labor market and society.
- Harmonizing the number of departments, pieces of equipment and faculty members, in order to maintain the quality of the educational process.
- Running training programs and courses to improve the level of faculty members.
- Participation of students in the evaluation processes that are available in education departments. This should be done to spread the ‘high-quality’ culture and to boost the student’s confidence in the respective educational institute.
- Installing an evaluation system in any department of the college of education, in order to evaluate the outcomes of education departments.
- Using state-of-the-art technologies for evaluation. This can be done by developing evaluation applications on the departments’ websites and students will be trained on how to use them.
- Holding monthly and periodical matches between departments to investigate, and consequently to assure the quality of, activities and level of performance.
- Periodically presenting the evaluation results to students, staff and society, in order to gain familiarity with the development of education departments of the college.
- Establishing performance standards that suit those set by international academic accreditation commissions, and evaluating the performance of departments every month to identify the degree to which they have met these standards. This helps to receive accreditation in the shortest possible time, as well as develops the performance of college’s departments.

Second: Installing a quality unit specific to the departments of the college of education. This should be done to ensure that the accreditation standards of college of education are met, to enhance the quality of teaching, to establish evaluation standards specific to the departments of the college, and to ensure that the high quality standards are met perfectly and the necessary procedures are followed.

The deanship of the university should directly assume control of these units and should also have the qualifications for solving problems and improving the performance. Furthermore, these units should be controlled by academicians having expertise in quality and university administrative affairs.

Results and Recommendations

First: Conclusion

1. The outcomes of colleges of education have a weakness in their performance. This weakness is attributed to different factors such as administration, non-updated programs and, sporadically, faculty members.
2. There is no mechanism for measuring and evaluating society's institutions' satisfaction of the performance of the college. This goes against the graduate tracking system.
3. Training programs dedicated to serve the society, as well as scientific consultations offered by colleges of education are of low quality.
4. Institutions of the labor market have not perfectly made use of the outcomes of the college of education, albeit these outcomes are characterized by inclusivity and can thus satisfy most of the needs of business sectors of the labor market.

Second: Recommendations

- 1- It is necessary for colleges of education to make their outcomes suitable for the needs and demands of labor market, in order to meet these needs and to ensure that outcomes get job opportunities appropriate for their specializations.
- 2- It is necessary to grant universities much independence and to avoid intervening in the decisions of the college of education, thereby ensuring quality of all its outcomes, and especially raising the qualitative level of graduates who are regarded as the most important outcomes.
- 3- One should focus on the learning processes and programs and, given that they improve the efficiency of educational outcomes and significantly contribute to quality assurance of graduates, one should regard them as equal to the usual academic programs.
- 4- It is important to attach weight to continuous improvement in all areas related to education quality, in order to ensure that the detected weaknesses are overcome and the achieved strengths are improved, thereby keeping up with the continuous scientific progress.

Results

We reviewed and analyzed the theoretical literature and the previous studies, and also investigated the results of previous studies. The most important result of the present study is that there is a relative weakness in the student—the teacher—in terms of cognition and skill in Jordan. This weakness is attributed to a lack of coordination and collaboration between colleges of education, local environment, society and market's needs. As a result, the education outcomes do not suit the prerequisites of development of other sectors. Furthermore, there is a weakness in the corporatism between colleges of education and general education institutes that aims to improve the practical training of the student—the teacher. There is no clear plan to regulate field training, nor is there enough time for the student to intern and practice. The mechanisms of evaluation do not take into account the nature and type of courses either. Instead, they rely on written tests as their main measure. This has caused a lack of creativity and excellence in the student, and a weakness in the practical skills of educational outcomes. There is also a defect in updating different education programs and plans in the colleges of education. Such an update should suit modern developments, development need, society and labor market.

Recommendations

In the present study a number of recommendations were concluded, the paramount of which was that colleges of education at Jordanian universities should update academic plans and, consequently, update education programs. Furthermore, they should diversify specializations so as to suit the market's needs. They should also develop their infrastructure by providing equipment, instructional aids, and evaluation tools that suit the nature of academic courses.

Plans and programs are to be updated according to the quality standards set by the local and international programmatic accreditation commissions. When developing educational plans, it is important that the current educational curricula of colleges of education be reconsidered. Moreover, it is necessary to coordinate with, and make the educational outcomes of colleges of education suit the demands of, labor market. In order for colleges of education to provide community service for their universities, qualified cadres—teachers—who have graduated should be continuously trained in practice. The training needs of faculty members at Jordanian universities are to be determined, as well as training programs should be suggested to them. It is also recommended that more scientific research and studies be done on the quality of educational outcomes in the Jordanian education sector, whereby we can gain more familiarity with this sector and improve it. In addition,

an attempt should be made to enrich Arab libraries with the education literature related to the quality of educational outcomes and programs of colleges of education.

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